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UPWARDS

Deliverable D6.2

Model Order Reduction Toolbox implemented

WP	6	Integrated System Simulation and Knowledge Extraction
Task	6.2	Model order reduction

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Deliverable abstract

This document reports about the **Model Order Reduction**, which we implemented in Task 6.2 and delivered as toolbox to the partners of the Upwards consortium. Partners use this toolbox for performing a rank reduction of models in the high dimensional data space of wind parks. Simulating wind parks by rank reduced models requires much less computation memory and time than their originating counterparts.

Deliverable Review

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1. Introduction

Deliverable 6.2 describes the model order reduction (MOR) toolbox, which we developed in Task 6.2. In UPWARDS we apply MOR techniques to speed up the simulation of the individual models by reducing the complexity while controlling the reduction error of the overall integrated simulation model and conserving the important details. We integrate the resulting toolbox into UPWARDS' integrated simulation framework `py_upwards` and provide it to partners at the Gitlab collaboration platform.

Figure 1 Concept of model order reduction

Goals of Tasks 6.2 Model order reduction

- Determination of the types of equations (PDEs) and phenomena of the models in WP2 – WP5
- Proposal and implementation support for MOR algorithms for models in WP2 – WP5 for increasing simulation speed, e.g., dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) [1] for data-based approaches or proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) [2] for equation-based approaches.
- Identification of an appropriate error metric and analysis of error propagation w.r.t. integrated system simulation.

Risks

Risk identified at project proposal state	Level of likelihood	Risk-mitigation measures
1. No access to equations for MOR	medium	Use equation-free methods (e.g., Dynamic Mode Decomposition)
2. Model complexity exceeds computational limits of MOR algorithms	Low	Split models and apply MOR to sub-models

Due to the fact, that the park model of WP2 is a central synchronization point, kind of a leading system of the overall simulation framework of UPWARDS and resulting due to high dimensionality in high computational cost in space and time, we put the focus on reducing the rank of the incorporated park simulation models of WP2. Furthermore, we concentrated our efforts to develop a

data-based, equation-free model order reduction toolbox, which will enable us in UPWARDS to generate rank-reduced models of all simulation systems (WP3-WP4) that are, in scope of UPWARDS' overall simulation platform, subsequent to the park model.

2. Type of Equation

The analysis of the equations of the different simulation tools of the partners (WP2-WP4) resulted in the observation that the underlying equations of the physical behavior are described in terms of partial differential equations (PDEs) or directly as higher order ordinary differential equations (ODEs). To solve the PDEs, usually a system of high order ordinary differential equations (ODEs) is created using approaches like Finite Volume or Finite element methods e.g., for atmospheric flow, wind park, wind turbine components modelling.

For example, the famous Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible fluid flows are used to explain the behavior of wind in a wind park. Here, the following assumption has to be made in order to apply it to flows of gases [6]: Since the influence of the pressure on the density of gases is small for flow velocities below 30% of the speed of sound, it can be assumed that the wind is behaving like an incompressible fluid. Wind turbine under normal operating conditions, operates between cut-in speed of 3 to 4 m/s and up to cutout speed of 25 m/s much lower than the speed of sound. The Navier-Stokes equation without additional source/sink term serves as the basis for the wind park model, however, it does not describe the interaction between the wind and the wind turbine, which is integrated as extra term in the momentum equation. This interaction e.g., will be modelled by the so-called actuator line model. The Finite Volume Method is used to solve the resulting set of equations and solving these discretized ODE equations are computationally demanding. The widely applied Finite Element Method for Elliptic Partial Differential Equations is related to the Finite Volume Method and primarily used in wind turbine components modelling and aeroelastic studies. The core principle of this method is to divide the area of interest into finitely many polyhedra - called finite elements - whose centers and the centers of their boundary surfaces will be treated as points in a discretization and which leads to a set of algebraic equations for each finite element. This results in very large systems, which need to be solved with very small step sizes to guarantee stability. Thus, we have an enormous computational cost in both memory and time.

3. Model Order Reduction Approach

The modelling approach for most of the subsystems in the simulation frameworks used by the partners of UPWARDS makes it difficult to employ many well-known MOR techniques. The Proper Orthogonal Decomposition in combination with the Galerkin projection [2] serves as example, since the application of the latter requires knowledge and access of the dynamic as well as on the algebraic equations, which due to complexity (here, within the framework OpenFoam) or due to legal issues are hard to access or to modify.

Thus, we decided to apply an equation free modelling reduction technique. We selected the dynamic mode decomposition (DMD), since it turns out in many applications to result in good approximations of the underlying high dimensional systems of equations. An equation free approach only requires snapshots of our computed solution at the interesting parts of the system covering the relevant inputs (inlet windows) and outputs. As it originates from the fluid dynamic community, its applicability to wind farms and turbines seems to be quite reasonable. DMD is a particular case of a technique called Koopman Analysis. The core feature of Koopman Analysis [5] is that it transforms a finite-dimensional nonlinear system into an infinite-dimensional linear system. This is achieved by considering (up to) infinitely many nonlinear measurements of the state vector rather than the state vector itself. In principle, this procedure is an extension of the argument space in order to smooth out the nonlinearities.

3.1. Dynamic mode decomposition [3]

As seen in chapter 2, we assume that in UPWARDS a system of ordinary differential equations (ODE) $\frac{dx}{dt} = f(x, t)$ underlays the majority of the wind turbine related simulators. We assume that this system function f is not explicitly given. However, based on simulation systems or real measurements, we have snapshot data $x(t_j)$ at different times $t_j = j\Delta t$ available.

The general idea behind the Dynamic Mode Decomposition is to approximate the system via a linear ODE $x_{j+1} = Ax_j$, which is an often valid assumption in operating points. Therefore, we split the system of snapshots into two matrices:

1. $X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{m-1}] \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times (m-1)}$
2. $X' = [x_2, x_3, \dots, x_m] \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times (m-1)}$, with $X' = \tilde{A}X$ and eigendecomposition of $\tilde{A} : (\Omega, \Phi)$.

There are two ways to calculate a solution $x(t)$ that approximates the snapshots:

1. Either we assume that $\tilde{A} = A$, then a solution of the ODE $x' = Ax$ is given by $x(t) = \Phi e^{\Omega^* t} b$ with b is calculated using the initial value.
2. Or we approximate the snapshots via $x_k = \Phi \Omega^k b$ and interpolate these approximations to $x(t) = \Phi \Omega^{\frac{t}{\Delta t}} b$.

Using the pseudo inverse X^+ we can state that $\tilde{A} \approx X X^+ \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$. The problem is that we get a huge matrix with this approach, which is expensive to calculate. To solve this problem, we use the SVD and we get the following algorithm:

1. Step:

- $X = USV^* \approx U_r S_r V_r^*$ via SVD such that $U \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$, $V \in \mathbb{C}^{(m-1) \times (m-1)}$ Both, U and V both are unitary. S is the diagonal Matrix of singular values σ_i in descending order. $U_r \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times r}$, $S_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, $V_r^* \in \mathbb{C}^{r \times (m-1)}$ are of lower dimension, because S_r is part of the matrix S that contains only the first r singular values.
- We can choose the rank r depending on the accuracy of the solution.

2. Step:

- $\tilde{A} \approx X X^+ \approx X V_r S_r^{-1} U_r^*$ where $X^+ = V_r S_r^{-1} U_r^*$
- $A_r = U_r^* \tilde{A} U_r = U_r^* X V_r S_r^{-1}$, remark : In practice we only calculate A_r .

3. Step:

- We calculate the eigenvectors and eigenvalues of A_r such that $A_r W = W \Omega$, $W = [\text{eigenvectors}]$, $\Omega = \text{diag}(\text{eigenvalues})$

4. Step:

- There are two ways to calculate DMD modes Φ (approximation of the eigenvectors of \tilde{A}).

standard DMD (projected modes):

- $\Phi = U_r W$ are the eigenvectors of $U_r U_r^* \tilde{A}$ with eigenvalues Ω . This is a good approximation if $U_r U_r^* \approx I$

exact DMD (exact modes):

- $\Phi = \Omega^{-1} X^T V_r S_r^{-1}$ are the eigenvectors of \tilde{A} with eigenvalues Ω

$$x(t) = \Phi e^{\Omega^* t} b = \sum_{k=1}^r \phi_k e^{\omega_k^* t} b_k \quad \text{or} \quad x(t) = \Phi \Omega^{\frac{t}{\Delta t}} b = \sum_{k=1}^r \phi_k \omega_k^{\frac{t}{\Delta t}} b_k$$

- We calculate the solution
- $x(0) = \Phi b \Rightarrow b \approx \Phi^+ x(0)$

While the DMD modes describe the spatial development of the solution, the dynamics describe its temporal evolution:

1. dynamics are given by $e^{\omega_k t} b_k, k = 1, \dots, r$
2. dynamics are given by $\omega_k^{\frac{t}{\Delta t}} b_k, k = 1, \dots, r$

We compared the error in between the DMD reconstruction of snapshots and the original snapshots by using the L1-norm. Due to the fact, that large areas in wind parks contain steady-state dynamics, we put special attention to measure error distribution in the spatial regions of interest surrounding each wind turbine.

4. Model order reduction toolbox

The contribution of WP 6.2 to the UPWARDS project is a toolbox extension of the developed library `py_upwards`. Partners of the UPWARDS consortium access the platform by using the Gitlab collaboration platform. The platform is hosted by Fraunhofer ITWM.

4.1. Features

- Input data given as specified in WP6.1
- Transformation of simulation results to standard CSV format, as we specified it in WP 6.1 (please refer to D6.1 Integrated serial simulation platform). The ability to parse this data, such that snapshot matrices can be populated with data from `OPENFOAM`, `SAMCEF`, or `STAR-CCM+`. This allows users to later-on compute rank reduced models on data generated by noise, blade and fatigue models.
- Application of the dynamic mode decomposition algorithms [4] on the system states within the domain to generate and persist rank-reduced system representations.
- Modal analytics of system states at certain 3-D subareas in time.

4.2. Use Case: Wind Park

The model order reduction toolbox provides users with following features:

- Easy to use configuration and execution of wind park simulation projects that contain one or more wind turbines. We use `OPENFOAM` as simulation runtime engine.
- Transformation of simulation results from `OPENFOAM` snapshot format to standard CSV format, as we specified it in WP 6.1 Visualization of the 3-D flow fields within the park to get early feedback. This also includes grids of high resolution (here, `OPENFOAM`'s snappy hex meshes). The visualization features comprise slicing and dicing of subareas within the park, e.g., to investigate the turbine's rotor, or the wake within the produced slipstream.
- Application of the dynamic mode decomposition algorithms on the fluid flow states within the wind park to generate and persist rank-reduced system representations.
- Modal analytics of fluid flow field states at certain 3-D subareas in time.
- Prediction of fluid flow states at each point in the park domain in time. Depending on the chosen rank of the reduced model, it is possible to reduce the simulation time from hours to seconds.
- Interpolation of fluid flow states in between simulated snapshots of given inlet wind velocities
- Grid transformation of fluid flow states nearby turbine rotors, such users can perform local investigations on turbulence effects.
- Generation of 2-D error visualizations, which allows users to perform spatial analyses of distributions of L1 distances between different versions of snapshots.

We proceed with describing this use case by examples and screenshots.

4.3. Examples

The following application examples of the `py_upwards` MOR toolbox show Python code, which results in rank reduced models of a wind park using `OPENFOAM`

Examples on using the toolbox

1. Create a simple steady-state park simulation with a single turbine positioned at $(x=0, y=0, z=0)$. The inlet velocity is set to $(9.0, 0.0, 0.0)$. A count of 5000 snapshots with a sample time of 0.1s will be generated. Each snapshot contains 577.481 grid points with a memory consumption of around 17 MB. In total measurements of velocity will sum up to 76.2 GB.

```
In [4]:
sim_type=simulation.STEADY
no_boundary_condition=True
t_intensity=10

sim = simulation.OFSimulationCase("park_sim_9", in_folder, sim_type=sim_type, no_boundary_condition=no_boundary_condition, t_intensity=t_intensity)

sim.NRELSMWRRef["TowerHt"] = 263

turbine_locations = [(0, 0, 0)]
inletFlowVelocity = [9, 0, 0]
startTime = 0 # in s
endTime = 500 # in s
delta_t = 0.02 # length of step
write_interval = 5 # steps

sim.setup_steady_state_simulation(
    start_time=startTime,
    end_time = endTime,
    delta_t=delta_t,
    write_interval=write_interval,
    park=turbine_locations,
    inlet_velocity=inletFlowVelocity)
```

2. Train a dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) model on 700 snapshots. 100 snapshots will be used for testing purpose.

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```
In [12]: used_snapshots = 700 # Training
recreated_snapshots = 100 # Testing
wasted_snapshots = 0
svd_rank = 8
exact = True

error1, dmd1, dmd_dict1 = dmd_func.DMD_execute(data_U, used_snapshots, recreated_snapshots, wasted_snapshots, svd_rank, exact)

print(error1)
```

Use the trained rank-reduced DMD model to recreate snapshots.

```
In [17]: data_dict_dmd1_U = dict()
data_dict_dmd1_U["data"] = dmd_func.reconstruct_snapshots(dmd1, 2, 1).real
data_dict_dmd1_U["dim"] = data_U["dim"]
data_dict_dmd1_U["name"] = data_U["name"]
data_dict_dmd1_U["delta_t"] = data_U["delta_t"]

print(np.linalg.norm(data_U['data'][:,0:1] - data_dict_dmd1_U["data"])/np.linalg.norm(data_U['data'][:,0:1]))
plot.plot_data(data_dict_dmd1_U, grid, 0, 0, variable="x", component="norm")
```

Examples on investigating flow fields by rank reduced models

The images Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4 show a visualization of a snapped surface from the front of a turbine's rotor. Figure 3 depicts a flow field at time t of a trained DMD model on snapshots of a 3-D park domain with an initial condition of inlet wind velocity of (9.0, 0.0, 0.0). Figure 4 shows the L1 norm of the error image, compared to the original snapshot at time t . It can be seen that the trained model performs some errors nearby the tips of the blades.

Figure 2 Original snapshot

Figure 3 DMD snapshot

Figure 4 Error between original and DMD snapshot

Figure 5 shows the gradient distribution of singular values of so-called POD modes on a log scale. It can be seen that the dominant system dynamic, here the rotation of the wind turbine, is represented by a single mode. This can be explained by a steady inlet wind velocity, which causes a constant rotation speed of the turbine's rotor.

Figure 5 Gradient Distribution of POD modes

The 2-D image in Figure 6 explains the dynamics of eigenvalues of eight DMD modes. Values inside the unit circle represent a damping effect of the underlying dynamics within the wind park.

Figure 6 Dynamics of eight DMD modes

Figure 7 to Figure 9 show a top view on a wind park with two wind turbines. They the original flow field state (x-direction), the rank-reduced recreation of this flow field state, and the L1 error distribution. The rank r to represent this system was $r=4$. Increasing the number of ranks would reduce the error rates that occur in the wake after the second turbine.

Figure 7 Original snapshot (Mean velocity contour plot in the mid plane of the wind turbine)

Figure 8 Snapshot reconstruction by DMD (Mean velocity contour plot in the mid plane of the wind turbine)

Figure 9 Error between original and DMD snapshot

The norm of the eight spatial DMD modes that are depicted in Figure 10 show the impact of each mode within a snip of a rank reduced systems with a rank=8. The model was trained on mean velocity values in a window of 60s. Therefore, the rotor appears as a circle.

Figure 10 2-D Distribution L2-Norm of DMD modes

The dynamic components of each mode are shown in Figure 11. As each mode is represented as complex values, the related dynamics contain two phases.

Figure 11 Frequencies (pair of real and imaginary parts) of mode dynamics

The images in Figure 12 to Figure 15 show real and complex parts of four modes on a system, which is represented by the 2-D cut-out window shortly in front of a rotor. The first mode represents the time invariant offset of the flow fields. Here, the imaginary part shows a uniform distribution. Subsequent modes represent the rotor rotation.

Figure 12 DMD mode representing the static offset, hence the imaginary part

Figure 13 DMD mode representing a rotation

Figure 14 DMD mode representing a rotation

Figure 15 DMD mode representing a rotation

The images in Figure 16 to Figure 18 show results from another transformed cutout of a wind park. Here, the front window in front of a rotor was rotated that way, that blade positions remain static. The three images show an original snapshot (Figure 16), a recreated snapshot of the DMD model (Figure 17) and the error in between (Figure 18).

Figure 16: Original Snapshot

Figure 17: DMD Snapshot

Figure 18: Error between original and DMD snapshot

5. Runtime Evaluation

In the Table 1, we depict the time different tasks required for four different simulation cases. We also include the dimension of the respective problem. Some entries are preceded by an expression of the form "(n)", where n gives us the number of CPUs that were used for the task. For simplification, we assume that all CPUs are of the same speed and the tasks were perfectly parallelizable, i.e., a process, which takes t seconds on n CPUs, would require n times t seconds on a single CPU.

Task	Case 1: U	Case 1: p	Case 2: U	Case 3: U	Case 4: U
Dimension	684000	225000	684000	11400000	2178000
Simulation	(4·)6.7h	(4·)6.7h	(4·)7.6h	(4·)9.8h	(12·)11.9h
Compute all SVs	4.1s	1.3s	4.3s	6.9s	11.5s
Rank 61 DMD	29.2s	9.4s	29.6s	44.2s	89.9s
Compute new Data	70.7s	23.4s	69.9s	116.9s	242.9s
<i>Rank 10 DMD</i>	8.3s	2.8s	8.4s	13.0s	27.8s
<i>Rank 30 DMD</i>	25.7s	8.5s	25.1s	42.1s	83.6s
<i>Rank 119 DMD</i>	37.5s	12.7s	38.4s	65.3s	109,1s

Table 1 Runtime comparison between simulations in OpenFoam and DMD

6. Conclusions

In this report, we documented the demonstrator of the model order reduction toolbox which we developed in task 6.2. The developed toolbox does not need access to the original equations and therefore can be applied to any kind of applications such as atmospheric flows, aero-elastic simulations of the wind turbine components, noise propagation. In the present deliverable, the proposed tools box has been applied to model a wind turbine. Partners of the UPWARDS consortium access the toolbox by using the Gitlab collaboration platform that is hosted by Fraunhofer ITWM.

Since we are very interested in promoting the next generation of scientists, this toolbox has been applied by a series of student's master and bachelor theses at Fraunhofer ITWM and currently we support bachelor work at UPWARDS partner SINTEF:

- Wolf, Tobias: Model Order Reduction using Neural Networks, 2021, Department of mathematics, University of Kaiserslautern, supervised by Prof. Dr. Tobias Damm.
- Burr, Julia: Analyseverfahren zur Wahl der Snapshots bei Anwendung der Dynamic Mode Decomposition auf Simulationsdaten von Windkraftanlagen (engl. Analysis method for snapshot selection when applying dynamic mode decomposition to wind turbine simulation)

data.), Bachelor thesis, 2020, Department of Mathematics, University of Kaiserslautern, supervised by Prof. Dr. Tobias Damm.

- Breuer, Eric: Dynamic Mode Decomposition for Wind Farm Models, Master thesis, 2019, Department of mathematics, University of Kaiserslautern, supervised by Prof. Dr. Tobias Damm.
- Weinberger, Stephan: POD-Galerkin Projection for Wind Farm Models based on incompressible Navier-Stokes Equations, Master thesis, 2019, department of Mathematics, University of Kaiserslautern, supervised by Prof. Dr. Tobias Damm.

7. References

- (1) J.N. Kutz, S.L. Brunton, B.W. Brunton, and J.L. Proctor. Dynamic Mode Decomposition: Data-Driven Modeling of Complex Systems. Other Titles in Applied Mathematics. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, 2016.
- (2) Francesco Ballarin, Andrea Manzoni, Al_o Quarteroni, and Gianluigi Rozza. Supremizer stabilization of POD-Galerkin approximation of parametrized steady incompressible Navier-Stokes equations. International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, 102:11361161, 2014.
- (3) Jonathan H. Tu, Clarence W. Rowley, Dirk M. Luchtenburg, Steven L. Brunton, and J. Nathan Kutz. On Dynamic Mode Decomposition: Theory and Applications, Nov 2013.
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